

تطوير طريقة تحليلية جديدة بتقنية RP-HPLC والتحقق من مصدوقيتها للتقدير المتزامن للداباغليفلوزين
بروبان ديول أحادي الماء والميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد في المواد الأولية والمضغوطات الملبسة بالفيلم
**Development and Validation of a New RP-HPLC method for the Simultaneous
Estimation of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate and Metformin
Hydrochloride in Bulk and Film-Coated Tablets**

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المخلص Abstract:

تظهر هذه الدراسة طريقة جديدة مطوّرة باستخدام الكروماتوغرافيا السائلة عالية الأداء بطور عكسي (RP-HPLC) للتقدير المتزامن لكلّ من الداباغليفلوزين (DAPA) والميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد (MET HCl) في كلّ من المواد الأولية وأفي المضغوطات الملبسة بالفيلم. تم إجراء الفصل باستخدام عمود InertSustain C18 بأبعاد (القطر الداخلي 4.6 ملم × 150 ملم، أبعاد الجسيمات 3 ميكرومتر) عند درجة حرارة 30 °م.

تم الكشف باستخدام كاشف مصفوفة الضوئية (PDA)، حيث تم قياس الداباغليفلوزين عند طول موجي 223 نانومتر، والميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد عند طول موجي 270 نانومتر.

تكوّن الطور المتحرك من مزيج الأسيتونتريل ومحلول وقاء الفوسفات (تم ضبط الرقم الهيدروجيني إلى 3.0 باستخدام حمض الأورثوفوسفور) بنسبة 55:45 (حجم/حجم)، بمعدل تدفق 1 مل/دقيقة وحجم حقن 60 ميكرو لتر. تم فصل الميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد والداباغليفلوزين عند أزمنة احتباس 1.366 دقيقة، 3.678 دقيقة على الترتيب.

كانت منحنيات المعايرة خطية ضمن النطاقات 1.0–10.0 ميكروغرام/مل للداباغليفلوزين، و 0.17–1.70 ملغ/مل للميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد.

أظهرت عملية التحقق من مصدوقية الطريقة نتائج مرضية من حيث الخطية، النوعية، المضبوطية، الدقة، المتانة، وملاءمة النظام. تؤكد هذه النتائج مصدوقية الطريقة وتوافقها مع معايير ICH Q2(R1).

This study presents a newly developed reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin (DAPA) and metformin hydrochloride (MET HCl) in both bulk drug form and film-coated tablets. The separation was achieved using an InertSustain C18 column (4.6 mm I.D. × 150 mm, 3 µm) maintained at 30 °C. Detection was carried out with a photodiode array detector, measuring DAPA at 223 nm and MET HCl at 270 nm. The mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile and phosphate buffer (pH adjusted to 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid) in a 45:55 (v/v) ratio, delivered at a flow rate of 1 mL/min with an injection volume of 60 µL. MET HCl and DAPA eluted at retention times of 1.366 min and 3.678 min, respectively. Calibration curves were linear within the ranges of 1.0–10.0 µg/mL for DAPA and 0.17–1.70 mg/mL for MET HCl. Method validation demonstrated satisfactory results

for linearity, specificity, accuracy, precision, robustness, and system suitability. These outcomes confirm the method's reliability and its compliance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines.

الكلمات المفتاح :Key words

داباغليفلوزين، ميتفورمين هيدروكلورايد، RP-HPLC، التحقق من الصلاحية، مضغوطات

Dapagliflozin, Metformin hydrochloride, RP-HPLC, Validation, Tablets

Introduction

Sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT₂) inhibitors, such as dapagliflozin (DAPA), play a key role in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved DAPA in January 2014 [1]. It appears as a white to off-white crystalline powder and is soluble in solvents such as methanol, ethanol, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and dimethylformamide (DMF) [2]. DAPA has a molecular weight of 408.9 g/mol and a chemical formula of C₂₁H₂₅ClO₆ (Figure 1). Its IUPAC name is (2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-2-[4-chloro-3-[(4-ethoxyphenyl)methyl]phenyl]-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxane-3,4,5-triol [3,4]

Figure (1): Chemical Structure of Dapagliflozin

Metformin hydrochloride (MET HCl), a member of the biguanide class, remains the first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes [5,6]. With a molecular weight of 165.62 g/mol and the formula C₄H₁₁N₅·HCl, MET HCl is chemically identified as 1,1-dimethylbiguanide hydrochloride. It is a white crystalline powder that is freely soluble in water, slightly soluble in

alcohol, and practically insoluble in acetone and methylene chloride [7,8].

Figure (2): Chemical structure of Metformin hydrochloride

DAPA and MET HCl are commonly formulated as film-coated tablets to enhance glycemic control in patients whose blood glucose levels are inadequately managed by metformin alone or in combination with other oral antidiabetics or insulin [8].

RP-HPLC is a well-established analytical technique widely used in pharmaceutical analysis. It is considered the gold standard for the simultaneous quantification of multicomponent formulations due to its high accuracy, sensitivity, reproducibility, and ability to separate complex mixtures and detect low concentrations. Previous studies have employed RP-HPLC for the estimation of Dapagliflozin (DAPA) and Metformin Hydrochloride (MET HCl). For instance, Afshan Urooj et al. developed an RP-HPLC method with detection at 285 nm using a PDA detector [9], while Mohammad Younes and Gowri Sankar introduced a validated, stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of MET HCl and DAPA in both bulk and dosage forms [10]. Additional methods include spectrophotometric approaches by Saad Antakli et al. [11], and first derivative UV spectrophotometry developed by B.R. Jani and colleagues for synthetic mixtures [12].

Furthermore, Bhavyasri K. (2021) proposed an RP-HPLC method focused on the simultaneous determination of DAPA and MET HCl [13], whereas Dhanshri et al. (2022) developed a stability-indicating RP-HPLC method specifically for tablet dosage forms, demonstrating its suitability for routine quality control and degradation studies [14].

The current research aims to develop a simple, accurate, and sensitive RP-HPLC method for the qualitative and quantitative determination of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride in both bulk form and locally available fixed-dose combination tablets. The method was thoroughly validated in accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, particularly given the absence of any official pharmacopeial method for this specific drug combination. It is important to highlight that a dissolution method for the same combination was developed and validated in our laboratory [15], and the analytical method presented in this study was specifically designed to support and enable such dissolution studies. This ensures the method's applicability in real-world formulation evaluation, routine quality control, and further pharmaceutical development.

Materials and Methods

Materials:

Dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate (purity 99.9%) was obtained from Hubei Derun Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. (Hubei Province, China), while Metformin hydrochloride (purity 99.7%) was supplied by Aarti Drugs Limited (Mumbai, India). HPLC grade acetonitrile and methanol were procured from Merck-Supelco (Germany), and orthophosphoric acid used in buffer preparation was sourced from Surchem (United Kingdom).

Method development and optimization of chromatographic conditions:

- Chromatographic Conditions:

Chromatographic separations were conducted using a C18 reverse-phase column (4.6 mm × 150 mm, 3 μm) under gradient elution conditions. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of 45:55 (v/v) acetonitrile and phosphate buffer adjusted to pH 3.0 with 85% (v/v)

orthophosphoric acid (OPA). An injection volume was 60 μL, and the flow rate was 1 mL/min. The analytes were measured with a PDA detector at 223 nm, 270 nm for DAPA and MET HCl, respectively, and the column temperature was controlled at 30 °C.

- Preparation of Buffer solution

A 10 mM disodium hydrogen phosphate ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) buffer was prepared by dissolving 1.78 g of $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 500 mL of double distilled water in a 1000 mL volumetric flask. The solution was placed in an ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution. The pH was carefully adjusted to 3.0 using 85% orthophosphoric acid. Finally, the volume was made up to the 1000 mL mark with double distilled water.

- Preparation of Stock Solutions

A standard stock solution of DAPA (500 μg/mL) was prepared by accurately weighing 10.01 mg of the drug and transferring it into a 20 mL volumetric flask. Methanol was used as the solvent to complete the volume.

For MET HCl, a standard stock solution (8.50 mg/mL) was prepared by dissolving 852.55 mg of the compound in methanol and diluting to 100 mL in a volumetric flask.

- Preparation of Standard solution

To prepare the working standard solution, 0.2 mL of the DAPA stock solution and 2.0 mL of the MET HCl stock solution were transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask. The mobile phase was added to bring the volume to the mark. The resulting solution contained 10.00 μg/mL of DAPA and 1.70 mg/mL of MET HCl.

- Sample Preparation

Twenty film-coated tablets, each containing 5 mg of DAPA and 850 mg of MET HCl, were weighed and finely powdered. An amount equivalent to one tablet was accurately weighed and transferred to a 50 mL volumetric flask containing methanol. The mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes to ensure complete extraction of the active ingredients. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter to remove any particulate matter. Subsequently, 1 mL of the filtrate was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with the mobile phase.

- Wavelength Selection

The UV absorption spectra of DAPA and MET HCl were recorded to determine their maximum absorbance wavelengths. As illustrated in (Figures 3 and 4), DAPA exhibited a λ_{max} at 223 nm, while MET HCl showed maximum absorption at 235 nm. Despite MET HCl having a higher absorbance at 235 nm, a wavelength of 270 nm was selected for its detection to facilitate simultaneous analysis of both drugs in a single injection without the need for prior dilution of MET HCl.

Figure (3): UV spectra for DAPA

Figure (4): UV spectra for MET HCl

Method Validation

The proposed chromatographic method was thoroughly validated following the guidelines set forth by the International Conference on Harmonization ICH Q2 (R1), ensuring its reliability and suitability for the intended analytical purpose [16, 17].

- Linearity

To assess linearity, five standard solutions of DAPA with concentrations of (1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and MET HCl with concentrations of (0.17, 0.50, 0.85, 1.20, and 1.70 mg/mL) were prepared. Each solution was injected in triplicate, and the resulting peak areas were subjected to

linear regression analysis using the least-squares method to evaluate the relationship between concentration and response.

- Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was evaluated through recovery studies. Sample solutions were prepared at three concentrations within the linear range: (5.55, 7.50, and 9.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) for DAPA, and (0.95, 1.25, and 1.55 mg/mL) for MET HCl. Each concentration was analyzed in triplicate. The mean percentage recoveries for both analytes were calculated, followed by the determination of the standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (RSD%) to assess the precision and accuracy of the method.

- Precision

Precision was evaluated at two levels: repeatability and intermediate precision [18].

Repeatability (Intra-day)

To assess repeatability, six consecutive injections of a standard solution containing 10.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of DAPA and 1.70 mg/mL of MET HCl were performed. The standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (RSD%) were calculated to evaluate the consistency of the measurements.

Intermediate precision (Inter-day)

Intermediate precision was assessed by preparing three different concentrations of DAPA (6.00, 6.75, and 7.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and MET HCl (1.20, 1.35, and 1.50 mg/mL), all within the established linear range. Each concentration was injected in triplicate. The average, SD, and RSD% were calculated for each concentration individually.

This analytical procedure was repeated on a second day, using freshly prepared samples at the same concentrations and injection protocol. The average, SD, and RSD% were then calculated for the combined results from both days for each concentration.

- Specificity

The specificity of the developed analytical method was assessed to ensure accurate identification and quantification of the active pharmaceutical ingredients in the presence of potential interfering substances such as excipients, impurities, and degradation products. In this study, specificity was evaluated by preparing a mixture of excipients including

(microcrystalline cellulose (9.04%), sodium starch glycolate type A (3%), hydroxypropyl cellulose (2%), magnesium stearate (0.5%), polyethylene glycol 3350 (0.8%), polyvinyl alcohol (4.5%), titanium dioxide (1.5%), talc (1.5%), and ferric oxides (1.5%) at concentrations equivalent to those found in a single film-coated tablet. This excipient mixture was injected consecutively three times, and the results were compared with those obtained from a standard solution containing 10.0 µg/mL of DAPA and 1.70 mg/mL of MET HCl to confirm the absence of interference.

- Sensitivity:

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) were calculated to evaluate the sensitivity of the proposed methods, according to equations (1) and (2).

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \frac{SD}{m} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times \frac{SD}{m} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

- Robustness

The robustness of the method was assessed by evaluating its performance under slight, deliberate variations in chromatographic conditions, simulating potential deviations that may occur during routine analysis. A standard solution within the linear range, containing 10.00 µg/mL of DAPA and 1.70 mg/mL of MET HCl, was prepared and analyzed. The robustness was tested by introducing minor changes to the flow rate of the mobile phase and the column temperature. The standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (RSD%) of the peak areas were calculated before and after implementing these changes. An RSD below 5% was considered acceptable, indicating the method's reliability under varied analytical conditions.

- System Suitability

System suitability testing is commonly performed in quality control laboratories to ensure that the entire analytical system including instrumentation, reagents, columns, and analyzers is functioning adequately and is appropriate for the intended analytical method. Parameters typically evaluated include retention time, tailing factor, number of theoretical plates,

resolution, and the precision of the measurements expressed as relative standard deviation (RSD%).

In this study, system suitability criteria were established based on the physicochemical properties of the analytes under investigation and the chromatographic separation conditions. For the proposed method, the following parameters were adopted:

A. Number of Theoretical Plates (N):

The theoretical plate count should not be less than 500 for peaks with retention times below two minutes, and not less than 1500 for peaks with retention times exceeding two minutes.

B. Resolution (Rs):

The resolution between MET HCl and DAPA peaks must be no less than 5.0 to ensure clear and effective separation of the two compounds.

C. Relative Standard Deviation (RSD%):

The RSD% for three consecutive injections (n = 3) should not exceed 2%, ensuring system precision and repeatability.

Therefore, the method's performance within these predefined limits is considered acceptable and confirms the suitability of the analytical procedure in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and reliability, in accordance with the ICH Q2(R1) guidelines.

Results and Discussion

Mobile Phase Optimization

The HPLC parameters were optimized to achieve both rapid analysis (run time < 6 minutes) and effective Resolution (Rs > 2) for the simultaneous quantification of DAPA and MET HCl. Various combinations of acetonitrile, water, and phosphate buffer were evaluated during the optimization process. The optimal chromatographic conditions were established using a mobile phase composed of acetonitrile and phosphate buffer (pH 3.0) in a 45:55 (v/v) ratio, with a column oven temperature maintained at 30 °C and a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min.

Under these conditions, the retention times were 1.364 minutes for MET HCl and 3.652 minutes for DAPA. Detection wavelengths were set at 270 nm for MET HCl and 223 nm for DAPA, as shown in Table (1). The chromatograms

presented in Figures (5, 6) demonstrates distinct and well-resolved peaks corresponding to MET HCl (1.70 mg/mL) and DAPA (10.00 µg/mL).

Table (1): Ideal chromatographic conditions of the developed method

Column	C18- reversed phase column, 150 x 4.6 mm 3 µm	
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (45:55% v/v) adjusted to pH (3.0) ± 0.1 with OPA	
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min	
Detection wavelengths	DAPA	223 nm
	MET HCl	270 nm
Column temperature	30 °C	
Detector	PDA	
Injection volume	60 µL	
Run time	6.0 min	

Figure (5): Chromatographic peak corresponding to MET HCl, observed at a retention time of 1.364 minutes (left peak)

Figure (6): Chromatographic peak corresponding to DAPA, observed at a retention time of 3.652 minutes (right peak)

Method Validation Data

The linearity parameters for DAPA and MET HCl are summarized in Table (2). As evident

from the data, both analytes exhibit strong linear correlations between concentration and peak area, indicating a reliable linear response within the studied ranges.

Table (2): Linearity by regression analysis (n=5).

Studied substances	Conc. Range	Slope	Intercept (b)	correlation coefficient (r)
DAPA	1 – 10 µg/mL	133969	4073.6	0.9990
MET HCl	0.17 – 1.7 mg/mL	506244	41729	0.9997

Calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak area versus concentration for both DAPA and MET HCl. The regression equations and corresponding correlation coefficients (r) for each compound are illustrated in Figure (6), demonstrating excellent linearity for both drugs.

Figure (6): Linearity of DAPA and MET HCl Accuracy of the method was confirmed through recovery studies. The percentage recoveries for DAPA ranged from 98.77% to 100.54%, while

those for MET HCl were between 100.33% and 101.72%. All recovery values fall within the acceptable range of 98%–102%, confirming the method's accuracy and reliability for simultaneous quantification of this drug combination, as detailed in Table (3).

Table (3): Results of the recovery studies

Substance	Theoretical Conc.	Found Conc. \pm SD	Recovery %	RSD %
DAPA ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5.55	5.58 \pm 0.01	100.54	0.179
	7.50	7.48 \pm 0.006	99.69	0.08
	9.50	9.38 \pm 0.01	98.77	0.107
MET HCl (mg/mL)	0.95	0.953 \pm 0.006	100.35	0.63
	1.25	1.27 \pm 0.006	101.33	0.472
	1.55	1.58 \pm 0.005	101.72	0.316

The relative standard deviation (RSD%) values for repeatability were below 1%, while those for intermediate precision were under 2%, indicating that the developed analytical method exhibits high precision. The precision results are summarized in Tables (4,5).

Table (4): Repeatability of DAPA and MET HCl using the suggested method

Injection No.	Found conc. of DAPA ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Found conc. of MET HCl (mg/mL)
1	10.01	1.68
2	10.08	1.68
3	9.95	1.67
4	9.96	1.67
5	9.95	1.67
6	9.94	1.67
Mean	9.98	1.67
SD	0.05	0.005
RSD %	0.501%	0.30%

Table (5): Intra-day and inter-day precision.

Substance	Conc. Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	RSD% (intra-day n=3)	RSD% (inter-day n=6)
DAPA	6.00	0.09	0.58
	6.75	0.08	2.57
	7.50	0.12	2.80
Substance	Conc. Range (mg/mL)	RSD% (intra-day n=3)	RSD% (inter-day n=6)
MET HCl	1.20	0.048	0.50
	1.35	0.155	0.30
	1.50	0.103	0.14

The chromatograms of the standard and placebo samples used in the specificity studies are presented in Figure (7).

Figure (7): Chromatogram obtained for the standard solution and the formulation excipients.

Table (6) presents the calculated LOD and LOQ values, showing that the proposed method provides sufficient sensitivity for detecting and quantifying the analyte at low concentration levels.

Table (6): LOD and LOQ values for the studied compounds

Drug	wavelength	LOD	LOQ
DAPA	223 nm	0.23 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.71 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
MET HCl	270 nm	0.046 mg/mL	0.138 mg/mL

Table (7) and Table (8) show the findings of the robustness study after small changes to the conditions of the method developed, and they

show the RSD% of the concentration for each level of both substances studied. The results of the robustness study, following minor variations in the method conditions, are summarized in Tables (6, 7), which report the RSD% values of the concentration at each tested level for both analytes.

Table (7): Results of robustness for MET HCl

Factor	Range	Measured percentage (%)	RSD%
Flow rate (mL/min)	0.9	102.32	0.16
	1.1	101.09	0.29
Column temperature (°C)	28	98.77	0.12
	32	98.64	0.16

Table (8): Results of robustness for DAPA

Factor	Range	Measured percentage (%)	RSD%
Flow rate (mL/min)	0.9	98.95	0.26
	1.1	99.55	0.39
Column temperature (°C)	28	101.33	0.13
	32	101.64	0.20

Additionally, the system suitability test results are provided in Table (9).

Table (9): System suitability parameters

Parameters	MET HCl	DAPA
Retention time (min.)	1.364	3.652
Resolution factor (RS)	–	7.78
Tailing factor t_f	1.86	1.52
Number of theoretical plates	735	3664

Application to commercial products

To evaluate the applicability of the developed method for routine quality control, five replicate injections (60 μ L) each of both the standard and sample solutions were introduced into the chromatographic system. The resulting chromatograms were recorded, and the corresponding peak areas were measured. The Relative Standard Deviation (RSD%) was

subsequently calculated to assess the repeatability of the method. The results are presented in Table (10).

Table (10): Results of Chromatographic Analysis of Pharmaceutical products Containing DAPA and MET HCl

Drug	Label claim (mg)	Amount found (mg)	Mean recovery % \pm SD	RSD %	
Product X	DAPA	5	5.101	102.02 \pm 0.102	0.10
	MET HCl	850	847.535	99.71 \pm 0.059	0.06
Product Y	DAPA	5	5.08	101.60 \pm 0.081	0.08
	MET HCl	850	847.45	99.70 \pm 0.1196	0.12

Conclusions

The results obtained from the developed analytical method demonstrated high accuracy, precision, and reliability for the quantitative determination of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and metformin hydrochloride in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method proved suitable for application to commercially available drug products.

Using the developed HPLC method on a Shimadzu chromatographic system, effective separation of the two analytes was achieved in a single injection, with detection at 223 nm for dapagliflozin and 270 nm for metformin hydrochloride. Importantly, no additional dilution of metformin hydrochloride was required, even at high concentrations.

Based on these findings, we recommend the adoption of this chromatographic method in quality control laboratories and pharmaceutical research facilities for the routine analysis of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate, either as a single active substance or in combination with metformin hydrochloride, given its demonstrated accuracy, precision, and high sensitivity.

List of abbreviations

DAPA	Dapagliflozin
MET HCl	Metformin Hydrochloride
RP-HPLC	Reversed Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography
PDA	Photodiode array
OPA	Orthophosphoric acid
SGLT ₂	Sodium- glucose cotransporter 2
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
ICH	International Conference on Harmonization
Conc.	Concentration
min.	minute
SD	Standard Deviation
RSD	Relative Standard Deviation
R _s	Resolution factor
t _f	Tailing factor
T ₂ DM	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest

Funding

Aleppo University, International Drug Manufacturing (IDM) pharma.

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Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their gratitude and thanks to the Research Laboratory

of the Faculty of Pharmacy, Aleppo University, as well as to International Drug Manufacturing (IDM) Pharma in Aleppo, Syria, for their invaluable help and support in this research.

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